

ISic0174

I.Sicily inscription 0174

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Found in 1883 among ancient construction materials found in the old castle of Termini

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano, inventory 86

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 19.5 cm

Width 29.5 cm

Depth 8 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D(is) M(anibus) s(acrum)

2. Euplia vi

3. xit an(nis) LV

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Reversed C symbol before numeral, interpreted as 'circiter'

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175737

EDR 076865

EDCS 10900654

Bibliography

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